

AQLI ZAIF O'QUVCHILARNI TARBIYALASHDA SENSOR TA'SIR ETISHNING KORREKSION AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada aqli zaif o'quvchilarni sensor tarbiyalashning korreksion mazmuni, uning bajaradigan umumlashtiruvchi funksiyalari, yordamchi maktabda o'quv tarbiyaviy ishlarni amaliy jihatdan amalga oshirish va ta'lim, tarbiya va rivojlanish chizmasining uchta komponentlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korreksion ish, sensamator jarayonlar, sensor rivojlanish, taktil-motor va ko'ruv, ruhiy rivojlanish, atrof-alam, predmet va hodisalar.

Yordamchi maktabda korreksion ish mazmunini to'g'ri aniqlash uchun korreksioni ta'lim tizimining barcha asosiy komponentlari bilan bog'lash muhimdir va faqatgina shundan keyin tuzilmani ichki tuzilishini va pedagogik mazmunining rolini ko'rib chiqish mumkin.

Korreksion ishning maqsadi, alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalarni umumiy ta'lim olishlar ijara yonida psixik va jismoniy funksiyalarini to'g'irlash, hayot va mehnatga tayorlashdir.

“Ta'lim“ atamasining o'zi va ushbu jarayon mohiyati ko'pgina tadqiqotlarda turlicha talqin qilinadi. Biroq “ta'lim” tushunchasi to'liq ta'rifni V.S.Lebedeva bergan bo'lib u o'z ta'rifida ushbu tushuncha tuzilishini ham ko'rsatgan: “Ta'lim bu ajdodlar tomonidan shaxs bo'lib yetishish uchun ontogenetik doirada bio ijtimoiy jarayonni aks ettiruvchi ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega tajribaning doimiy ravishda berilishini jamoat tomonidan tashkil qilinishi va normaga solinishi jarayonidir. Ushbu jarayonda mazmun, shakl tomondan xarakterlanuvchi uchta tuzilishli, aspektlar farqlanadi: shaxsga tajribani o'zlashtirishni ta'minlovchi ongli; shaxsga xos xususiyatlarni tarbiyalash, shuningdek jismoniy va aqliy rivojlanish; ta'limda asosiy faoliyat o'quv faoliyati hisoblanadi”.

Shunday qilib, ta'lim o'zichiga uchta asosiy qismni: o'qitish, tarbiya va rivojlantirishni oladi.

O'qitish bevosita o'quvchilarning tajribani o'zlashtirishlariga qaratilgan, tarbiya va rivojlantirish esa bilvosita amlaga oshiriladi. Uchta jarayonning barchasi tarbiya, o'qitish va rivojlantirish butunlikda bir – biri bilan uyg'un tarzda amalga oshirili bularni ajratish chegaralash deyarli mumkin emas.

Defektologiya va maxsus pedagogika bo'yicha ko'pgina ishlarda qoidaga ko'ra korreksiyani bola rivojlanishi bilan bog'laydilar. Bu alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalarning rivojlanishidagi ikkilamchi nuqsonlarni to'g'irlashga qaratilganligi uchun asoslangandir. Biroq korreksion pedagogik ish haqida gapirilganda uni ta'limning uchlik birligi chizmasidan: o'qitish, tarbiya, rivojlantirishdan ajratib o'lmaydi.

Yordamchi maktabda o'quv tarbiyaviy ishlarni amaliy jihatdan amalga oshirishda korreksion rivojlantirishni maxsus tashkil etuvchi va yo'naltiruvchi jarayon sifatida korreksion ta'lim va tarbiyada ajratilmaydi hamda alohida mavjud bo'lmaydi.

O'quvchilar rivojlanishi ta'lim mobaynida va tarbiya jarayonida amalga oshirilganligi sababli korreksion ta'sir ham ushbu faoliyatda ishtirok etadi.

O'z - o'zidan maxsus ta'lim ham umumiy ta'lim singari uchlik birligidan iborat bo'lib, korreksion o'qitish, korreksion tarbiya, korreksion rivojlanishdan tashkil topadi.

Korreksion ta'lim-psixologik va jismoniy rivojlantirishdagi kamchiliklarni yengish yo'llari va vositalari haqidagi bilimlarni egallash, hamda egallangan bilimlarni qo'llash usullarini o'zlashtirish.

Korreksion tarbiya ijtimoiy muhitda moslashishga imkon beruvchi faoliyatning predmetli o'ziga xosligiga teskari variantalanuvchi shaxs sifatlari va unga xos xususiyatlarni tarbiyalash (idrok qilish, mehnat, estetik va boshqalar)

Korreksion rivojlanish aqliy va jismoniy rivojlanishdagi kamchiliklarni (oldini olish) to'g'irlash, nuqsonning neyro dinamik mexanizmlari kompensatsiyasi va saqlangan sensor doirasining ruhiy va jismoniy funksiyalarining takomillashtirilishi.

Istalgan ta'lim va tarbiya bir vaqtning o'zida ma'lum darajada rivojlantiradi. Bu esa korreksion jarayonlarga ham talluqlidir. Shu bilan birga rivojlanishning korreksiyalanishi faqat bilim va malakalarni o'zlashtirish bilangina bog'lab bo'lmaydi. Maxsus ta'lim jarayonida ruhiy va jismoniy funksiyalar qayta ko'riladi, nuqsonni kompensatsiyalash mexanizmi shakllantiriladi, ulaga yangi xarakter beriladi. Korreksion rivojlanish bilan birga shaxsning ijtimoiy tajribani o'zlashtirish qanday ketishiga qarab ma'lum darajada shaxs xususiyatlari va holatining o'zgarishi yuz beradi va ular yig'iladi. Korreksion ish davomida aqliy jismoniy, axloqiy jihatdan o'z-o'zini boshqarish, o'z faoliyatini tashkil etish va boshqarish qobiliyati, ijtimoiy mehnatda mo'ljal olish malakalari rivojlanadi. Korreksion komponentlarning (ta'lim, tarbiya, rivojlanish) mutanosibligi V.S.Lebedeva tavsiya etgan chizmada aks etgan. Ta'lim, tarbiya va rivojlanish chizmasi uchta komponentning o'zaro bog'liq ligiramzi sifatida uchta o'zaro kesishgan aylana ko'rinishida tasvirlangan.

Birinchidan, maxsus ta'lim konsepsiyasidan kelib chiqqan holda korreksion pedagogik ish maxsus maktabda o'quv tarbiyaviy jarayonning defektologik yo'nalganligini aniqlaganligi sababli tizimda markaziy o'rinni egallashi kerak.

Ikkinchidan, korreksiya umumiy ta'limning tashkil etuvchi qismlari chorrahasida joylashgan bo'lishi va shu bilan bir vaqtda alohida yordamga muhtoj o'quvchilarning ta'lim, tarbiya va rivojlanishini amalga oshirishda o'ziga xos qirralarga (yo'nalishlarga) ega bo'lishi kerak.

Uchinchidan, maxsus ta'lim tizimida korreksion pedagogik jarayonning hajmi va ahamiyatiga ko'raunga ta'lim qismlari chorrahasida muhim o'rin berilishi kerak.

To'rtinchidan, korreksiya ijtimoiy tizim sifatida muhitga mustaqilchiqa olishi kerak, chunki tizim alohida emas, balki aniq ijtimoiy sharoitda funksiyallashadi. Muhit korreksion pedagogik jarayon uchun aniq element emas, balki uichki qism sifatida kiruvchi atrof muhit sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ijtimoiy muhit ko'rib chiqila yotgan jarayonning barcha darajalariga ta'sir qiladi, biroq bu ta'sir turlicha bo'ladi. Avvalambor, u maxsus ta'limda jamiyat maqsadini aks ettiradi: o'quvchilar shaxsining har tomonlama rivojlanishi va ularni shakllanishishi, ularning ijtimoiy mehnat realibitatsiyasi, nuqsonning kompensatsiyasi, insoniyatning ijtimoiy tajribasini oson shaklda o'zlashtirish.

Korreksion pedagogik ishning barcha tizimi alohida yordamga muhtoj bolani atrof - olam mavjudliklariga rehabilitatsiya qilish va ijtimoiy moslashtirish uchun undalgan bo'lib, uni barcha insonlar bilan birgalikda mehnat va jamiyat hayotiga kira oladigan va jamiyatga foydasi tegadigan teng huquqli va faol mehnatkash qilib yetishtirishdir.

Alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalarni o'qitish va tarbiyalashda korreksiyaning nuqsonni kompensatsiy aqil ish usuli sifatida ko'riladigan fikrlarni uchratish mumkin. Biz umumiy va maxsus ta'lim natijasida shaxsni shakllantirish haqida gapirar ekanmiz, korreksion pedagogik ish

natijaga (kompensatsiyaga) mos holda ko‘rilishi kerak, chunki pedagogik mohiyat ham miqdoriy, ham sifat jihatdan aynan unga bog‘langan. Korreksiya nisbatan keng tushuncha bo‘lib, aynanu alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalar rivojlanishidagi nuqsonlarni kompensatsiya qilish darajasini aniqlaydi, maxsus ta‘lim tizimi hamda maxsus maktabdagi o‘quv tarbiyaviy ishlarning organik asosi hisoblanadi.

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